

GOALS AND TASKS OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

Shakhlo Khakimovna Kharatova

Associate Professor of Tashkent State Transport University

ORCID identifier: 0000-0002-6535-0197

Email: SHAHLO-70@mail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7112416>

Abstract: This article contains scientific and theoretical opinions about the goals and tasks of teaching English.

Key words: Educational system, English language, methodology, goals and tasks, form of education, pedagogue.

Learning teaching English in non-philological higher educational institutions has its own characteristics and requires the use of special teaching methods. The teaching methodology is a holistic system, consisting of such components as educational conditions, goals, content, methods, and tools.

It is known that any goal arises out of necessity. A goal is a general direction in education, a plan for solving a specific task(s). Practical, general educational, educational and developmental goals are recognized in foreign language teaching.

Vocational (professional) goals are also set in educational institutions specializing in foreign languages.

The purpose of teaching English is to form the skills of using the studied language as a means of exchange of ideas, to increase students' cognitive activity, and to develop their speech and professional skills. All the goals are interrelated and require each other in the educational process.

The meaning of the practical goal can be understood from its name: it is intended to use the studied language in the student's activity (practice). Despite the fact that the term learning a language for practical purposes has been given different definitions and descriptions in the methodology of foreign language teaching, among teachers there are also misconceptions about learning a language for practical purposes, such as understanding oral speech or speaking activities. Such an understanding is considered one of the wrong interpretations, and it is appropriate to emphasize that giving/receiving information is carried out not only in oral speech (speaking, listening comprehension), but also through written speech (reading, writing).

Methodist scholars do not have the same opinion on the existing interpretations of the practical purpose of the methodology of foreign language teaching, that is, they interpret the practical purpose in different ways in different conditions.

A group of foreign language teaching methodologists accepted the term practical goal in the sense of mastering the language at an insufficient professional level, depending on the requirement of the specialty or the interest of the language learner, which allows to learn it more thoroughly later. At the same time, knowledge of a foreign language at a non-professional level, learning the main types of speech activity, according to another point of view, knowing all types of speech activity or conducting oral and written communication in a foreign language are discussed within the framework of practical goals.

Another group of Methodist-scientists recognized the practical goal of expressing thoughts in a foreign language orally and in writing and understanding the thoughts of others. There are also guardians of this concept as teaching the culture of the people whose language is being studied.

According to the modern concept, the practical goal is to provide students with communicative (speech communication), linguistic (language knowledge), country studies (the country where the language is being studied) and linguocultural (the culture of the peoples whose language is being studied) information. requires the formation of speech skills. In the English language program, as a practical goal, it is necessary for students to know the following:

1. Reading and understanding of sectoral, socio-political and scientific-popular literature on the chosen specialty.
2. Ability to communicate in English orally and in writing within the framework of the program requirement.

The final practical goal of teaching English to students is the formation of speech skills and competencies such as reading, oral speech (speaking and listening comprehension) and writing. In short, learning English for practical purposes means getting the necessary information and conveying it to others using this language. The acquired information serves to increase the level of knowledge of students, educate and develop them.

The practical purpose is to serve as the basis and conditions for education, upbringing and development of the student's personality through communication in English. At the end of the education, the student will be able to understand (listening or reading) the learned English speech and express his/her opinion in this language (speak and write).

According to the Law "On Education" and the "National Program of Personnel Training", the main task of secondary schools and non-philological higher educational institutions is to improve the intellectual, moral, aesthetic and physical development abilities of a person in all aspects. it was specially emphasized that it is necessary to create favorable conditions for education and upbringing as much as possible, as well as to form national pride and national moral qualities in students.

These tasks require the teaching of all subjects included in the curriculum of this educational institution to be subordinated to this goal. English, which is considered as a subject of general education, contributes its share to education and upbringing and comprehensive development of students, along with other subjects. Before expressing an opinion about the general educational goal of the English language, it is permissible to dwell on some thoughts and considerations about the didactic interpretation of this goal.

Learning as a type of activity is interpreted as follows in pedagogy:

- ☒ formation of certain knowledge, skills and qualifications in students;
- ☒ forming certain thoughts, worldviews and beliefs in them;
- ☒ to make students become educated, cultured, well-rounded people at a certain level;
- ☒ is to develop their skills related to a specific profession.

Valuable opinions have been expressed in many studies on the general educational purpose of the foreign language subject. There are two types of students who study English for general educational purposes -

- (1) new knowledge and information about the language,

(2) absorb life and professional information obtained through language. The first type is aimed at acquiring language-related information, which includes rules and concepts for interpreting English language material (vocabulary, grammar and pronunciation). Units and new events used in the process of learning English are interesting for students and enrich their language experience.

The second type of information, life and professional information, is reflected in English texts. They are the surroundings of the student, our homeland Uzbekistan (Geographical position of Uzbekistan, Independence of Uzbekistan, History of Uzbekistan, Administrative subdivision of the Republic of Uzbekistan, etc.), the country(s) where the language is being studied (Great Britain, Political system of the USA, Parliament of Great Britain, Holidays of the USA and Great Britain, etc.) and we can observe that it is given in field texts in the college direction. Reading the above texts, firstly, enriches the general knowledge of the students with new information such as culture, art, history, literature, customs, traditions of these countries, and secondly, the specialized texts in English reading has a positive effect on enriching students' professional knowledge.

In English, the general educational goal is realized during the practical acquisition of the language. Practical knowledge is the main way to educate.

Education is a social phenomenon that appeared at the beginning of human society and serves the interests of mankind. At the same time, education is also a means of ensuring communication between generations. Each period had its own educational methods and tools. In ancient times, education was viewed as one of the forms of mastering the experiences of the older generation. Education was carried out mainly in the processes of work (hunting, cattle breeding, farming, etc.) and by conducting ceremonies related to various traditions. At that time, it was planned to educate physically fit and strong people. The change and development of the social system and production relations also influenced the improvement of the educational process.

Education is a pedagogical process organized for the purposeful improvement of the personality, which provides an opportunity to regularly and systematically influence the student's personality.

The following principles of education have been recognized in research:

- ☒ that education is aimed at a specific goal;
- ☒ humanitarian and democratic principle of education;
- ☒ connection of education with life and work;
- ☒ priority of national-cultural and universal values in education;
- ☒ taking into account the age characteristics of students in education;
- ☒ consistency and systematicity of education;
- ☒ unity and continuity of educational effects, etc.

The main goal of education is to form a fully developed, intellectually and morally perfect person. Students of the non-philological higher educational institution in the process of mastering the basis of general and specialized subjects acquire skills such as specialized skills, in-depth general knowledge, broad outlook, professional training, computer literacy, and continuous improvement of their knowledge. Among these, it is also necessary to cultivate in students the feelings of discipline, responsibility for their work, and dedication to the development of the country.

The educational goal is expressed by the educational importance of the subject of English. As students acquire knowledge, skills and abilities in English, they develop love for work, respect for workers, pride of the Motherland, friendship, camaraderie, and at the same time, moral, aesthetic, provides international education.

A perfect person is a person who is patriotic, people-loving, spiritually rich, morally pure, tolerant, who has kindness, goodness, hard work, honesty, and Eastern thought in his heart, who knows and respects his history and national values. He is also a modern man who is aware of the most advanced scientific achievements in world civilization, armed with universal ideas of world culture.

English language plays an important role in raising such a person.

This goal is mainly realized in foreign language material in two ways. Firstly, the direct education of the language learner (student) is observed in the educational process (greeting, saying goodbye, reacting to the surroundings in the same language), and secondly, such an educational process in the content of listening, speaking, reading and writing English language material. there are aspects that lead the student to enlightenment, satisfy his spiritual need.

It is known that in the English language education of a higher educational institution, texts on socio-economic, artistic, political, cultural, educational and industry topics are given for reading, and the information obtained from them is used by the student. it is required to be directly relevant and useful for education.

In addition, in teaching English, the educational target language is realized by studying the speech culture, ethics, and lifestyle of the nation(s) being studied.

Educating students through English language education: a) in class; b) it is carried out in the course of extracurricular activities (by holding various events, parties).

There is another professional goal in the teaching methodology, which is implemented in specialized educational institutions. Today, this goal is interpreted differently by researchers. In our opinion, it seems necessary to explain the concepts of "specialization", "profession" and "professional orientation" first.

Specialization (expertise) means having special theoretical knowledge, skills and competence in a specific field, for example, in the field of English language specialization. As the concept of profession, it is meant to use the English language in practice in a specific activity. Foreign language specialists are trained only in higher educational institutions related to this field. In such educational institutions, students have to study certain theoretical and practical subjects of this language in order to acquire a specialization in English. In non-philological higher educational institutions, all general educational and professional (general professional and special) subjects in the curriculum add the appropriate share to acquire a certain specialty. Having students read specialized field texts in English enriches students' general knowledge, including having a positive effect on their thorough mastering of field terms related to the profession. So, the English language helps students to develop their skills in a specific professional field.

The essence of professional orientation of education is to form the professional qualities of a person, to create favorable conditions for the formation of future professional qualifications. This is definitely within the scope of a professional goal.

In the English language education of non-philological higher educational institutions, due attention is paid to the education of students, and by achieving the above goals, the

personality and professional skills of future junior specialists are formed, which means that the developmental goal is achieved.

The developmental goal is determined by the expansion of students' worldview in the process of learning English. Learning English increases students' logical thinking (thinking, understanding, analysis, generalization), develops independent work skills. The developmental goal is manifested in the development of the skills of analyzing language materials, summarizing, drawing conclusions, and independently understanding the meaning of words. Therefore, raising the level of students in English language teaching from the bottom to the top, intellectually developing, improving the content, and ensuring that they grow intellectually is the first task that is expected from the realization of this goal. The second task is to improve students' feelings in learning English, to improve their perception and understanding of external influences with the help of senses and analyzers. Thirdly, the development goal requires strengthening the internal drive (motivation) to work and study.

The developmental goal is realized through speech acts. Its difference from the general educational goal is that the practical application of the acquired information or information content and the skills of its acquisition are included in the scope of the developing goal. Education is the basis of intellectual development. The goals of English language teaching have their own characteristics in high school and non-philological higher education.

In the process of learning English, based on the goals and tasks set for the subject, the student's communicative competence (ability) is formed, that is, the skills of learning the language as a means of spoken communication are formed. Speech competence consists of linguistic (language knowledge), social and cultural knowledge (social and cultural knowledge), speech skills and skills.

In terms of communicative competence, students should have the following practical knowledge: use language material in a speech situation; being able to think in prepared and unprepared monologues and pairs; such as mastering the types of reading (acquaintance, study, observational reading), getting information by reading the original and adapted text.

The ideas presented in our study are related to the interdependence of educational goals. Unity of education and upbringing is one of the leading principles in foreign language education. In the process of education and training, the student's mind is formed, his feelings and emotions develop, and behavioral habits necessary for social life are formed.

Ensuring the unity of education and upbringing depends in many ways on the proper organization of this process, effective use of various teaching methods. Especially to ensure the unity of education and upbringing:

- ☒ the correct organization of the content of the presented educational materials from a scientific and ideological point of view;
- ☒ full use of available opportunities to reveal the educational and educational essence of the studied subject;
- ☒ thorough and solid assimilation of the taught knowledge;
- ☒ it is of particular importance to increase students' interest, activity and initiative in the educational process.

This chapter presents opinions on the current situation of foreign language (English) teaching in secondary general education schools and non-philological higher educational institutions, the interpretation of the concept of educational conditions, and the linguo-didactic analysis of teaching goals.

The term linguodidactic refers to the concepts of where, to whom and for how long English language is taught. When defined using linguo-didactic terms, the personality characteristics of the language learner (age, general level, language experience, number of students in the class (group), the type of educational institution and foreign language in the curriculum) allocated class hours are included in the analysis.

A goal is a general direction in education, a plan for solving a specific task. Practical (communicative), general educational, educational, developmental and professional goals are recognized in the methodology of foreign language teaching. These goals apply to all educational institutions. However, they were interpreted in a unique way for secondary schools and non-philological universities.

Students of this educational institution acquire the basic general education knowledge in order to become mature members of the society while learning English. characteristics are developed.

References:

1. . INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH; Kharatova Sh.Kh; "Экономика и социум" 3 (82) 2021 www.iupr.ru
2. "THE IMPORTANCE OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS" KHARATOVA SHAKHLO KHAKIMOVA; "SCIENCE AND EDUCATION" IN VOLUME #2 ISSUE #5, MAY 2021;
3. "PROBLEMS OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING AND ITS SOLUTION" Kharatova Shakhlo Khakimovna; «Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире» ISCIENCE.IN.UA Выпуск 4(72) ч. Стр 60; ISSN 2524-0986.
4. Харатова Ш.Х. ЭФФЕКТИВНЫЕ СПОСОБЫ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА; Academy 2 (53) «Олимп» 2020;
5. Shakhlo Khakimovna Kharatova; TENDENCIES OF DEVELOPMENT OF DISTANCE EDUCATION IN GLOBAL TRANSFORMATION; Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences 10. 2021;
6. Kharatova Shakhlo "USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS" Science and Education ISSUE 3, March 2022;

